

The Amalgam of Rule and Justice: Striking Harmonizations on the Protection of Traditional Knowledge of Indigenous People on The Emerge of Intellectual Property Regime in Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 30, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 31, 2022</p>	<p><i>The ratification of Law No. 7 year 1994 concerning The Establishment of WTO following TRIPS agreement raising awareness on the protection of intellectual property rights internationally. Traditional knowledge of indigenous people is a wealth of the nation that has to be protected, but in recent development and existence, it is weak in terms of protection of intellectual property rights. Many cases found the fact that developed countries are taking advantage of the traditional knowledge from developing countries such Indonesia due to the lack protection of it. The different idea of Intellectual Property Rights protection on TRIPS which more take sides to the private property and monopoly is absolutely contrary to the communal ownership of indigenous people on their traditional knowledge. The different interpretations of the "prior act" and public domain of the traditional knowledge that come in debate also raising a juxtaposition between the invention and synthesis of the knowledge and the product. Indonesia does not have sui generis laws governing traditional knowledge. Therefore, this research conduct to create a progressive law to realize the protection and utilization of traditional knowledge. This research results that the digital database of communal intellectual property is an initiative of the Director General of Intellectual Property which is exceptional at protecting traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions. In addition it can address to build the innovation model of intellectual property rights of traditional knowledge protection through legal protection and defensive protection mechanism of Traditional Knowledge in Indonesia Intellectual Property Rights Schemes.</i></p>
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Introduction

Numbers of international bodies have been involved in negotiations and treaty drafting about traditional knowledge protection in the scheme of intellectual property rights. World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) defines traditional knowledge as follows: "Knowledge, know-how, skills and practices that are developed, sustained and passed on from generation to generation within a community, often forming part of its cultural or spiritual identity". According to WIPO's document, traditional knowledge is not limited to one particular knowledge but refers to a very broad range of knowledge. What separates traditional knowledge from other knowledge is its attachment to certain communities and this distinct characteristic that gives it traditional characteristics. WIPO classify traditional knowledge into agricultural knowledge, scientific knowledge, ecological knowledge, medicines knowledge including related medicine and remedies, biodiversity-related knowledge, expressions in the fields of music, dance, songs, handicrafts, elements of language, and moving cultural objects. Traditional knowledge is included in the scope of intellectual work that comes from the ideas, concepts, or discoveries from community groups. Traditional knowledge embodies the identity and personality of Indonesian as a nation that can also be utilized economically for the sake of prosperity and welfare of society. Traditional knowledge is a term used by WIPO to provide an outline of a cultural work that is traditional in nature and is owned by traditional community groups. Traditional knowledge process is the result of innovation and creation from humans in terms of knowledge, art, and literature.

TRIPS Agreement in the World Trade Organization given rise internationally of the public concerns to worldwide patenting. The birth of the World Trade Organization (WTO) as a result of the 8th round of the Uruguay Round, has had an impact on the birth of agreements on trade-related to aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights or TRIPs). Reasons for consideration of the agreement of TRIPs as part of annex 1C Approval of the Establishment of the World Trade Organization (WTO) is that Intellectual Property Rights (later written as IPR) can affect international trade, that IPR plays an important role in economic development. As a product of globalization TRIPs was agreed upon as a minimum standard for IPR protection that places absolute private ownership. Not included and regulated

genetic resources, folklore and traditional knowledge as part of IPR in TRIPs. These three assets, especially traditional knowledge, are assets of communal property that have long existed in traditional societies in developing countries for generations and meet the qualifications to be protected as IPR. However, back to the beginning of the purpose of the formation of TRIPs which are the results of ideas and insistence of developed countries, where they do not want restrictions on access to further use of genetic resources, folklore, and traditional knowledge possessed by developing countries. Traditional knowledge of indigenous people is a source of knowledge related to human life that can be commercialized. In fact, there is an estimate that the value of selling products that use traditional knowledge in the form of genetic resources each year ranges from the US \$ 800 billion. Traditional knowledge is also used by many researchers as the starting point of their research to obtain patents. The intellectual property right of indigenous knowledge and cultural heritage is unique due to the contrary concept of intellectual property right in TRIPs which is exclusive and individual private property to the communal ownership of indigenous people which is open and elusive.

Indonesia is blessed with its abundance of biological and cultural biodiversity nationwide. The utilization of traditional knowledge must be in synergy and harmony with the protection of its rights otherwise the indigenous people as the inventors will be victim of the violation of intellectual property right on their traditional knowledge. IPR on traditional knowledge potentialities is the assets for Indonesian development if its properly managed efficiently and effectively. Developed countries include France, Japan, the Netherlands, Britain and the United States clearly refused to recognize the existence of communal ownership as a collectivity, especially when discussing The Draft United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. The resistance of developed countries is certainly opportunistic because this can hamper the access of developed countries to utilize traditional knowledge of developing countries such as Indonesia through biopiracy and misappropriation.

Protection of traditional knowledge is needed by developing countries such as Indonesia, at least based on the following reasons: (1) The potential of traditional Indonesian knowledge which has economic benefits that are factually utilized by developed countries including the United States and Japan for the pharmaceutical industry cosmetics without benefit sharing with Indonesia; (2) Injustice experienced by Indonesia as a developing country over ownership of traditional knowledge that is not protected as IPR, while developed countries carry out biopiracy and misappropriation of traditional knowledge of Indonesia; and (3) Local people do not know that their traditional knowledge from generation to generation has economic benefits, especially traditional knowledge about medicines so that the government have moral duty to provide protection to the rights of these local communities in term of relevant national laws and, as a practical matter, sufficient investment in the innovation of traditional knowledge in order to deliver the value of protection to its holders. In practice, a lot of traditional wealth is owned by people in the archipelago who simply disappear or change ownership to other countries. For example, since the days of our ancestors we have known *tempe*, traditional Indonesian food with soybean raw material is an original idea of Indonesian society. Unfortunately in its development when *tempe* was widely known even to foreign countries, other countries with advances in technology and high awareness of IPR patented it as intellectual property as a result of their initiative. For example, the United States patented anti-cholesterol *tempe* and Japan patented *tempe* with antioxidant compounds, but the slow public awareness to patent *tempe* as an authentic Indonesian product, in the long run it could cause economic losses for Indonesia. There are still many other products of Indonesian people such as traditional medicines, arts and literary works that have not received legal protection. Various obstacles become the reason why the works and products of the nation have not received legal protection in terms of recognition and appreciation of IPR, among others regulations that have not fully supported the implementation of IPR, there is still low public awareness to register their work or thoughts, lack of documentation of data, and characteristics of knowledge traditional which is generally communal.

Although efforts to protect traditional knowledge are important and have been carried out in an international context through the WIPO mechanism and in the national context, it began to be carried out, namely by establishing Law No. 11 of 2013 concerning Ratification of Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits of the Convention on Biological Diversity (Nagoya Protocol About Access to Genetic Resources and Equitable and Balanced Distribution of Profits that Arise from Their Utilization On the Convention on Biological Diversity) which also regulates traditional knowledge related to genetic resources, but the use of traditional knowledge also needs to be done in view of the large amount of traditional knowledge belonging to the Indonesian people which was hijacked by developed countries without fair distribution of benefits to Indonesia. At present the IPR regulation is included in Law No. 14 year 2001 concerning Patent, Law No. 15 year 2001 concerning Trademarks, Law No. 19 year 2002 concerning Copyright, Law No. 29 year 2000 concerning Protection of Plant Variety, Law No. 30 year 2000 concerning Trade Secrets, and Law No. 18 year 2002 concerning the National System of Research, Development, and Application of Science and Technology which mentions the regulation of traditional knowledge. In practice, even though there are already intellectual property law instruments, many of the works of Indonesian people that have been

communally hereditary are patented by foreign citizens and provide economic benefits to them. For example, using traditional knowledge about herbal medicine and traditional medicines.

Regarding the traditional knowledge of indigenous people, Malaysia has some strengths on it due to the traditional knowledge of medicinal plants also the creation of a depository of knowledge on the traditional uses of tropical herbs among Malaysians has been suggested as a way of expanding product development. Many allude to the unique confluence of Asian health traditions found in Malaysia and say this cumulative knowledge could be used to advantage. A continuous effort is taken from the Malaysia government to document that knowledge to build up a rich database of medicinal plant applications and protecting it for the sake of the nation. Literature review has been done to find related journals about this issue, but research about the implementation of progressive law toward this issue never been done. Thus, this research is new and relevant to conduct. The existing research found related to the issue are:

1. Susy Frankel, *Traditional Knowledge, Indigenous Peoples, and Local Communities*, The Oxford Handbook of Intellectual Property Law, 2018, This paper situates the claims for protection of traditional knowledge in the international intellectual property (IP) context. In order to address the overlap with IP and provide protection against misuse of traditional knowledge, this research analyses the role of international bodies and has been involved in negotiations and treaty drafting related to the issue.
2. Graham Dutfield, *TRIPS-Related Aspects of Traditional Knowledge*, Case Western Reserve Journal of International Law, Volume 33 Issue 2 2001. This paper describes how the mainstreaming of Traditional Knowledge as a TRIPS-related issue achieved and explain why so much effort was made to achieve it. In addition, this paper shows how developing countries use Traditional Knowledge to influence their compliance with TRIPS.

The research about Indonesia's sui generis laws governing traditional knowledge never been taken. Therefore, this research aims to decode a progressive law to realize the protection and utilization of the traditional knowledge that synergist with the characteristic of the regions, among others are human resources, natural resources, environment and infrastructures as Indonesia has abundant biological and cultural biodiversity nationwide. This research will analyze the concept of legal ownership legal who becomes the rights holder in the protection of Traditional Knowledge and to know how they form of legal protection is given to Traditional Knowledge. As a comparative study, this research will also address how the innovation model of intellectual property rights of traditional knowledge protection in Malaysia, also create a model for strengthening the IPR-based indigenous community through legal protection and the development of traditional knowledge on the international trade This research is expected to contribute significantly, both theoretically and practically.

I. Problems

The formulation of the problem to be studied are:

1. How the identification problem of indigenous peoples, local communities, and the scope of traditional knowledge in Indonesia?
2. How the intellectual property frameworks and protection of traditional knowledge?

II. Research Method

The methodology used in this article is normative juridical with a statutory and doctrinal approach. Secondary data that has been collected is then analyzed by normative analysis. It analysis based on legal norms, legal doctrines and theories. In this analysis focussed on the use of content analysis methods and constructive analysts. For analytical techniques, the interpretation of the theory is used as a technique by means of dialogue between data on one side with legal norms, legal doctrine and legal theory on the other. With such analysis, it is expected that deviating analysis - taking can be avoided.

III. Discussion

1. How the identification problem of indigenous peoples, local communities, and the scope of traditional knowledge in Malaysia and Indonesia

The protection of traditional knowledge in Indonesia is still experiencing obstacles. When analyzing using the legal system theory of Lawrence M. Friedman, which includes three components or elements, namely legal structure, legal substance and legal culture. Then the barriers to enforcing IPR protection for traditional knowledge can be qualified, namely:

1. Structure of law:

Structure, namely the entire existing legal institutions and their apparatus.

- a. There is no clear procedure and cooperation among ministries in Indonesia to organize the documentation process and data-base of traditional knowledge in Indonesia. The Ministry of Culture and Tourism and the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, the Director General of IPR, carry out a separate inventory of traditional

knowledge. There is no clear line of coordination regarding which ministry will be assigned to carry out the documentation process and data-base on traditional Indonesian knowledge.

b. Good collaborative governance has not been built. Asynchrony and lack of coordination in handling cases can be caused by weak networking and cooperation between institutions. This is largely due to the high sectoral ego which still surrounds most public agencies in Indonesia (K quote: Killia, 2012). The right solution to solve the ego-structural problem is collaboration (K quote: Gray). At one level, the condition is because of the complexity and complexity of a problem, it is necessary to establish cooperation between government agencies, which this concept is known as collaborative governance. Collaborative governance refers to the formulation of governance, where one or more public agencies are directly involved with non-state stakeholders in a formal, consensus-oriented, deliberative decision-making process that leads to the formulation or implementation of public policies, or it can be program or asset management. public. (Ansell and Gash, 2008). Collaborative governance is aimed at achieving certain objectives related to the implementation of government programs or policies. However, in reality, especially in this case is the protection of traditional knowledge, the government has not shown a clear and carefully designed collaborative governance mechanism concept regarding the division of duties and authorities of each institution.

c. Uninline focuses on and purpose between community and government. Community think on how to protect, while government how to commercialize. The main objective of Indonesian national law is to regulate the use of intellectual property rights (HKI) contained in traditional knowledge and to regulate its commercialization, but not to regulate the maintenance or preservation of traditional knowledge. This can be read in the consideration of the PTEBT Bill which reads: that ethnic or ethnic diversity, and intellectual work which is a cultural heritage of high value, has in fact become an attraction for commercial use so that the utilization needs to be regulated for the benefit of the community. .

d. There is no documentation effort on traditional knowledge and the community who carry it (custodian). There is no documentation and data base made by the state that compiles the work or knowledge that is categorized as Indonesian TKF. The absence of a written document regarding this Traditional Knowledge has become one of the reasons for the patent office being granted with the consideration that there is no comparative document (prior art) which could invalidate the invention in question. This is very detrimental to the indigenous people as the owner of this traditional knowledge.

e. The government's efforts only reached the inventory process and were limited to keris, puppets, and batik.

2. Substance of Law:

Namely the entire legal rule, legal norms and legal principles, both written and unwritten.

a. There are no definite rules regarding the protection of PTEBT. The bill that was previously drafted and planned has not yet been passed.

b. There are only 1982 and 2002 Copyright Laws which give copyright to Indonesia's cultural heritage to the state and have also been mandated by Presidential Regulation No. 78 of 2007 concerning the Ratification of Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage.

c. A Bill on Traditional Knowledge and Traditional Cultural Expressions has been drafted (RUU PTEBT), but the coordination between the relevant ministries is not clear. Article 1 point 17 of the RUU PTEBT only defines the Minister as "the Minister who handles government affairs in the field of Protection and Utilization of Traditional Knowledge Intellectual Property and Traditional Cultural Expressions". The RUU PTEBT should have clearly regulated which institution or ministry is assigned to carry out documentation and compile a data-base on PTEBT.

d. There needs to be a sui generis law. The most important substance of the sui generis law is the clear recognition that local people are the "owners" of the traditional knowledge concerned. Customary law or customary law can be an alternative source or material for formulating the rights of local communities in the sui generis law.

e. The principles in customary law that can be accommodated in the sui generis law include: 1) the provisions in the sui generis law are simple; 2) The sui generis law should not neglect elements based on religious norms. This is in line with the customary law system which is religious in nature; 3) the sui generis law should still be based on a social system that values togetherness highly; 4) the sui generis law must be able to guarantee or at least provide a high possibility that the use of traditional knowledge (including knowledge in the field of biodiversity) can actually provide welfare for the community in general.

3. Legal Culture:

Namely opinions, beliefs, habits, ways of thinking, and ways of acting, both from law enforcers and from members of the community about law and various phenomena related to law.

a. The characteristics of Indonesian society are still characterized by collective or communal and religious systems, so that the behavior of the people is still imbued with and guided by this value system. Thus, creating laws based on different value systems will only cause problems in their implementation.

b. Prismatic society. Traditional society in Indonesia is a transitional society. The word "transition" itself refers to a stage in time between a certain past and a state in the predicted future. In other words, in this case, a

transitional society is a society that is or is changing to new values. The nature of society in developing countries is a transitional society, namely between societies that have both traditional and modern characteristics. Fred W. Riggs places a transitional phase in the development of a society as a prismatic society which when drawn a linear line lies between what is known as the fused model society as a traditional society and the diffracted society for a modern society. This prismatic society theory from Fred W Riggs can be used to analyze a new form of construction from the reconstruction of traditional community legal culture related to traditional knowledge management, which is related to the reconstruction of values that are the source of norms in order to manage the natural potential and special characteristics of the community. existing traditional societies to create prosperity and welfare so that the results of development and economic empowerment of traditional communities can be enjoyed by all people fairly and equally. Reconstructing the legal culture must start from changing the values that will be embodied in these norms. Cultural change must be carried out in order to adapt to existing developments and needs even though culture is not the only determining factor, but through cultural change it is expected to be able to shape behavior in accordance with development goals. New construction on legal culture is carried out by juxtaposing the ideal construction and existing construction of legal culture in traditional societies. Options for normalizing traditional knowledge management through strengthening community participation and government institutions that can encourage active community participation in order to achieve justice, balance, and sustainability, so that later these values are later on their way so that they can be understood and have uses for the interests of the community are translated into measurements. which is normative or concretized in the form of norms. The direction of a legal culture that is built for the prosperity and welfare of traditional communities in the management and utilization of traditional knowledge is carried out through efforts to manifest progressive values so that they continue to carry the values of virtue by considering local wisdom, sustainable sustainability, sustainable development, integration, partnership of the parties involved in the utilization. and management of traditional knowledge through active community participation aimed at empowering traditional communities, equitable value, consistency, justice, legal certainty, decentralization, accountability, recognition of local communities and traditional communities so that substantial behavior can be achieved (the spontaneously generated law), namely mutual cooperation, honesty, cooperation, social courtesy, social care as a symbol of participatory society, good life and good behavior and character so that the welfare of traditional communities includes material welfare, namely clothing, food, shelter and immaterial, namely the need for a sense of justice can be fulfilled properly.

c. The majority of people consider the issue of IPR protection and the commercialization of traditional Indonesian knowledge to be less urgent than the risk of extinction of traditional knowledge due to the lack of recognition and attention from the government, as well as the absence of documentation efforts on traditional knowledge and the community who carry it (custodian).

d. The purpose of protecting traditional knowledge in international forums is to preserve (preservation) traditional knowledge, while protection of IPR is a consequence of the preservation of traditional knowledge.

e. Actually, traditional communities also cannot accept the abuse and commercialization of their traditional knowledge, but these two things are not their main concerns. Their main concerns are: The sustainability of their culture; The existence of a system that can maintain and transmit their culture to the next generation

f. Traditional societies strive to achieve a balance between providing protection to their culture and giving access to everyone to use it for the creation of new creativity and innovation.

g. Not implementing a consistent process. An inventory of local traditional knowledge that has been carried out by the community and local government has not been followed up with a verification process, documentation and data-base compilation by the central government. This resulted in some local communities stopping making inventions of their traditional knowledge.

h. Lack of funding. It is true that the process of documenting traditional knowledge can be costly and time-consuming, because it must be accompanied by a verification process to avoid future disputes and controversies.

i. Lack of participation from the community and many parties. If participation can be maximized, the documentation costs borne by the government can be reduced if together with the community and local government, the central government also involves media companies in Indonesia that actively publish unique Indonesian traditions that can be categorized as traditional knowledge.

j. Tripartite participation. To reduce the cost of documenting this traditional knowledge, the government can also involve national private companies whose products are mostly made based on traditional Indonesian knowledge. There are also national and international foundations that can be involved by the government in this traditional knowledge documentation project, because these foundations have long independently published traditional Indonesian knowledge (One media company in Indonesia that has a commitment to promoting Indonesian culture is the KOMPAS Daily. For example: Traditional cosmetic companies, such as: PT. Mustika Ratu and PT. Sari Ayu; Herbal medicine companies, such as: PT. Air Mancur, PT. Nyonya Meneer, PT. Sido Muncul, etc. For example: Yayasan Dana Bakti, who has published a serial encyclopedia entitled The Indonesian Heritage Series; Harapan Kita Foundation; and Ford Foundation.

k. Lack of legal awareness of the protection of PT. The lack of understanding of the concept of protection of traditional knowledge among legal officials is also caused by the lack of socialization by the government of the Bill on protection of traditional knowledge to the public and legal officials in Indonesia. Although the traditional knowledge bill was included in the 2010-2014 Prolegnas, very little is known about the traditional knowledge bill and the government's concept of protecting traditional knowledge.

2. How the intellectual property frameworks and protection of traditional knowledge

The concept of Traditional Knowledge first appeared in international legal instruments during Convention on Biological Diversity in 1992 which signified the emergence of awareness from developing countries to protect Traditional Knowledge. United Nations, Convention on Biological Diversity 1992, article 8 (j) defines Traditional Knowledge as follows: Traditional knowledge is "Knowledge, innovation and practices of Indigenous and local communities embodying traditional lifestyles relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity". This convention had been ratified by Indonesia through Law Number 5 of 1994 on Ratification of the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity, State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 41 of 1994, and Supplement to the State Gazette Number 3556.

Regulations regarding the protection of the rights of traditional communities to traditional knowledge in Indonesia are regulated in Law No. 19 of 2002 concerning Copyright, Law no. 14 of 2001 on Patents, Law no. UU no. 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry, Presidential Regulation No. 28 of 2007 concerning Ratification of the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, Presidential Decree No. 16/1997 concerning the Ratification of the Patent Cooperation Treaty, and international conventions in the field of PTEBT, among others, the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage, the Convention on Biological Diversity; 2) Secondary sources of law include the PTEBT Bill, the Copyright Bill, the Patent Bill, the Indigenous Peoples Protection Bill, WIPO Model Law for Folklore Protection 1982, WIPO Draft Treaty on Protection of Folklore, WIPO Draft Treaty on Protection of Traditional Knowledge, WIPO-IGC Draft of the Protection of Traditional Cultural Expressions / Expressions of Folklore: Revised Objectives and Principles, WIPO-IGC Draft of the Protection of Traditional Knowledge: Revised Objectives and Principles.

Traditional knowledge is knowledge developed by indigenous people or intellectual works based on tradition. This knowledge includes methods of cultivation and processing of plants, medicine, arts, and food-drink recipes. In addition, a knowledge can be said to be traditional knowledge when that knowledge:

1. Taught and implemented from generation to generation;
2. Is knowledge which includes knowledge about the environment and its relationship with everything;
3. Holistic character, so that it cannot be separated from the community who built it;
4. Is a way of life (way of life), which is used jointly by the community, and therefore there are community values.

The protection of traditional knowledge is important because it is a source of knowledge related to human life that can be commercialized. Until now, a lot of traditional knowledge has been used by many researchers as a starting point for their research to obtain patents.

The concept of ownership for Traditional Knowledge can be further developed to not only be able to be owned by the community, whether it is groups or individuals, but also can be owned by the state so that it becomes national Traditional Knowledge, especially for Traditional Knowledge concerning the lives of many people. This concept of ownership has been applied by Thailand in their regulation for Traditional Medicinal Knowledge.

The position of the state as custodian in the conception of communal ownership of Traditional Knowledge is deemed appropriate if we following this train of thought: First, all natural resources must be controlled by the state, because the state is the highest form of authority that represent people's sovereignty in all fields, starting from law, politics, and economics. This is to prevent gaps in the use of natural resources if owned by individuals. Second, this type of control is expected to ensure more equality in the utilization of natural resource production. Consequently, access to Traditional Knowledge must be subject to state sovereignty. Therefore in order to mitigate these problems, the Directorate General of Intellectual Property, Ministry of Law and Human Rights, has developed a National Data Center Application for Indonesian Communal Intellectual Property. The goal is to provide a transparent and comprehensive national communal intellectual property data center that can be easily accessed anywhere and anytime by the public. Ideally, traditional knowledge as "tacit knowledge" can be transformed by incorporating elements of modern science and technology so that it becomes "explicit knowledge" in accordance with the "state of art". One of the examples is the traditional knowledge of the Bugis people regarding the design of the Pinisi ship, if transformed by incorporating modern physics such as fluid mechanics, it will produce ships with traditional design but still incorporate modern technology.

Although traditional knowledge has been mentioned in several international agreements, it has not been explicitly protected by international forums that specifically regulate IPR. Likewise, IPR regulations in Indonesia do not explicitly regulate the protection of traditional knowledge. Therefore, there needs to be improved protection in IPR regulations in Indonesia, especially the 2001 Patent Law. The agreement in the Convention on Biological Diversity in 1992 stipulates that the use of Traditional Knowledge related to its use

must establish the principle of equitable sharing of benefits to indigenous peoples as the original owners of this Traditional Knowledge. In general, the commercial use of Traditional Knowledge is aimed at the interests of the national economy, especially for the welfare of indigenous peoples as owners of Traditional Knowledge. Reasonably, Indonesia as a country abundance in traditional knowledge should take an active role in increasing the use of the principle of equitable sharing of benefits of Traditional Knowledge to its indigenous people. To realize this goal, the government needs to oversee the course of commercialization by collaborating with NGOs and indigenous peoples themselves. There are two type of activities that always underlie the commercialization of Traditional Knowledge, namely: First, Bioprospecting, an effort to find sources for the manufacture of new drugs through cooperation between traditional knowledge user and the provider. Second, Biopiracy, the action of taking and exploiting Traditional Knowledge without the permission of the provider and is used to benefit the user.

Ideally, bioprospecting is the type of activity that should get government support and empowerment considering that it is in line with the objectives of national development. As a consequence, access to and commercialization of Traditional Knowledge, including discussion of benefit sharing procedures, is only intended for bioprospecting activities, while biopiracy needs to be prevented and prohibited. In practice, the parties involve in using Traditional Knowledge can be categorized into three groups, namely as follows:

1) *Commercial users*

These users typically consist of researchers and scientists working for the biotechnology industry such as pharmaceutical companies (discovery of biologically active substances); Agricultural technology business (discovering new varieties of crops by increasing resistance to certain pests and diseases); or Chemical and petrochemical companies (developing commercial applications of organic raw materials).

2) *Traditional users*

They are local communities and indigenous peoples whose live depend on the traditional knowledge that exist in their living environment. Users usually use and develop Traditional Knowledge for the benefit of their group livelihood. The knowledge gained through this kind of development is passed on from generation to generation from one generation to the next. Sometimes the activities of using, utilizing and developing traditional knowledge are closely related to the cultural and spiritual activities that exist in the local community or indigenous peoples.

3) *Academic users*

Users in this category usually look for samples of plants and animals for various purposes, one of which is for commercial purposes. Another objective is for non-commercial activities and purely for the development of science and technology.

Although in general, indigenous peoples in Indonesia approve of benefit sharing over their Traditional Knowledge, but for some they may not want to share their Traditional Knowledge with other parties, for example because their Traditional Knowledge has certain sacredness or is related to their beliefs. Therefore, in order to respect the rights and traditions of indigenous peoples, it is necessary to immediately implement regulations (in this case a Government Regulation) which regulates obtaining prior informed consent thus giving rights to indigenous peoples in deciding whether they are going to allow others to make use of their Traditional Knowledge. These approval is important, since it is one of the conditions to obtain permit for permit to utilize Object of Cultural Advancement and Traditional, refer to Law Number 5 of 2017 on Cultural Advancement, State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 104 of 2017, and Supplement to the State Gazette (Number 6055, Article 5 letter e and Article 37 paragraph (2) letter a. Prior informed consent from indigenous peoples will provide legality for other parties to utilize this Traditional Knowledge therefore avoiding conflicts between the government and indigenous peoples who own Traditional Knowledge.

Benefit sharing can be done in several way such as monetary compensation, be it cash payments or ongoing royalties. Furthermore, benefit sharing can also be done in a non-monetary compensation. For indigenous people in Indonesia who rarely put economic value or potential for commercialization of their Traditional Knowledge, let alone from the perspective of IPR, non-monetary compensation will be more desirable than monetary compensation. Therefore, the most suitable regulation for benefit sharing is actually a model that has been practiced for centuries in Indonesia, which has enriched Indonesian Traditional Knowledge, to wit, new products or works made based on Indonesian Traditional Knowledge must be returned and made available to communities who who have cultivated said Traditional Knowledge.

Indigenous people feel more valued if their existence is recognized and protected without having to change the lifestyle that they believe in. The form of equitable benefit sharing from parties who utilize Traditional Knowledge outside the indigenous peoples who owns the knowledge, does not always have to be in the form of material gain (money), but can be realized through improving the Human Resources of indigenous peoples through skills training and education to preserve their existence and developing a technology consortium between the central government, local governments, NGOs and indigenous peoples who own Traditional Knowledge.

Benefit sharing can be given directly to the indigenous peoples through the customary institutions that cover them. The reason to share the benefit is because indigenous peoples have carried out the utilization and preservation of Traditional Knowledge continuously and from generation to generation. Traditional knowledge that has been passed down from generation to generation is an intellectual property owned by indigenous peoples and logically is their right. Benefit sharing between indigenous peoples and those who will use and or develop this Traditional Knowledge must be immediately stipulated through a Government Regulation as an implementing regulation of the Law Number 5 Year 2017 on Cultural Advancement Article 37 paragraph (1), (2), (3), and (4). This regulation on benefit sharing aims to provide legality for traditional knowledge of indigenous peoples.

The regulation regarding sui generis law related to communal intellectual property rights in Indonesia are still self-contained. This causes ineffectivity in enforcing the law, therefore benefit sharing is yet to be applied appropriately. Protection of Intellectual Property in the Law on Electronic Information and Transactions is inherently part of criminal law. Naturally these hamper the effectivity to enforce the law and does not solve the problem at hand. India implements digital database as part of the mechanisms used to protect their traditional knowledge. India builds Traditional Knowledge Digital Library of India, which is created under eight ministries with direct supervision under its prime minister. In this database, India lists medical treatments such as yoga, ayurvedha, anani, verda which are 4 components of Indian Traditional knowledge, written in various Indigenous languages, rewritten or translated into various languages, uploaded into a database that explicitly affirm it astraditional knowledge of India. (Fulvio Mazzocchi, 2006, 466). This is to prevent similar cases with turmeric case from happening again. This digital database is used for patent examination and is an effective defensive protection mechanism in India.

Indonesia has started to develop their own digital database of communal intellectual property as the implementation is of mandate from Government Regulation on Registration with the aim of taking an inventory of genetic resources and traditional knowledges in Indonesia

Inventory is part of defensive protection measure. By carrying out defensive protection, it minimizes the occurrence of unlawful abuses against traditional culture of a society. Attempt taken by various countries and communities as defensive protection measure is by building a database of traditional culture in the respective country. The state can use this database as a comparative document (prior art) for claims against the intended traditional knowledge and/or traditional cultural expressions. In retrospect, the benefit of having an inventory of traditional knowledge and/or traditional cultural expressions are:

1. Inventory, as evidence that a traditional culture belongs to Indonesia, if it exists in Indonesia. Naturally, it will be helpful to refute a foreign party ownership claims of said culture.
2. Inventory can be used as a comparative document (prior art) for the use regarding any intellectual property rights. It is often problematic especially in Indonesia because there is yet to exist inventory of traditional cultures
3. Inventory of cultures can be used as a first step in further cultural protection. For example, can be used as a basis for applying benefit sharing in case foreigners want to use said culture.

Conclusion

Identification of traditional knowledge related to intellectual property rights, namely the occurrence of indigenous peoples' ignorance of their own expertise. The government must take over the protection of these communal intellectual property rights by various means, one of which is by digitizing the database. Digital database of communal intellectual property is an initiative of the Director General of Intellectual Property which is exceptional at protecting traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions. This could be a solution to the ineffectiveness of the sui generis law, which is still self-contained. This is also the only possible measure are because government regulations on traditional cultural expressions are yet to see the light of day, looking at lack of progression regarding the bill, while the only regulation that touch on the subject is Cultural Advancement Law. Indonesia already has a bill on traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions but it has not yet been passed. There are still many debates and corrections from various parties. These delays only lead to more and more exploitation of Indonesian Traditional Knowledge and Traditional Cultural Expressions by other more developed countries. The obstacle related to this program is that even though database has been developed by several bodies of ministries, namely the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, Ministry of Environment and Forestry, the Ministry of Health in regards to traditional medicines, the Ministry of Education and Culture in regards to cultural works but efforts to integrate all of those are still in process. It takes a strong political will to coordinate all these ministries to integrate existing data.

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